

Instructions to upload EcoStack research outputs to Zenodo

Step 1

- Log-in to “EcoStack” Zenodo community <https://zenodo.org/communities/ecostack>
- If **not** existing user, suggested option is to log-in with or ORCID.
- Otherwise, sign-up/register with email
- Once you are logged in, you will be redirect to a page of Zenodo where you have to search for EcoStack community clicking “communities”

Recent uploads

March 2, 2020 (v2.2.0) Software Open Access

View

- Here type “EcoStack”

Communities created and curated by Zenodo users

Showing 0 to 10 out of 4263 communities.

Sort by ▾

- You will be redirect to a page where EcoStack project is listed. Here click on “View”

Communities created and curated by Zenodo users

ecostack

Showing 0 to 1 out of 1 communities.

Sort by ▾

EcoStack - Stacking of ecosystem services: mechanisms and interactions for optimal crop protection, pollination enhancement, and productivity (773554)

Agriculture has to face the great challenge of balancing the demand for high productivity, imposed by the global increase of human population, with environmental impacts and social acceptability of new production strategies. EcoStack will develop...

Curated by: francescocaracciolo

[View](#)

- You will be redirect to the EcoStack page

Step 2

- Click on New Upload button (Fig. 1)

Fig. 1.

EcoStack - Stacking of ecosystem services: mechanisms and interactions for optimal crop protection, pollination enhancement, and productivity (773554)

Recent uploads

Search EcoStack - Stacking of ecosystem services: mechanisms and interactions for optimal crop protection, pol

Community

EcoStack

EcoStack - Stacking of ecosystem services: mechanisms and interactions for optimal crop protection, pollination enhancement, and productivity (773554)

- Choose the file you intend to upload (figure 2.1) and click “start upload” (Figure 2.2) or fill-in required fields (marked with a red star).
- Type European Commission Funder Research “OperanAIRE” as community. (Figure 2.3)

Fig. 2.

Step 3

Complete all required information (Upload type, Basic information, License, etc.)

- If a **DOI** has already been assigned, can enter this otherwise Zenodo will register a new DOI clicking on “reserve DOI”(fig. 3).

Fig. 3.

- Access rights should be specified as **Open Access** (figure 4)
- All outputs (publications, videos, data etc.) from EcoStack projects **must have funding information given.**
Specify: European Commission (EU) and EcoStack or 773554 to identify upload as part of EcoStack project (fig. 4).
- Completing other information fields are optional

Fig. 4.

Licenserequired ▾

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

License *

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the Other licenses available (Other (Open), Other (Attribution), etc.). The supported licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org and spdx.org. If you think that a license is missing from the list, please contact us.

Fundingrecommended ▾

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

European Commission (EU)

Start typing a grant number, name or abbreviation...

✕

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the Additional Notes field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

[+ Add another grant](#)

Step 4

Press "**Save**" to save your upload for editing later.

When ready, press "**Publish**" to finalize and make your upload public.

For any problems please feel free to contact francesco.caracciolo@unina.it